

REMOTE CONTROL SYSTEM FOR OPTICAL RADIATION DIRECTION IN DISTRIBUTED MONITORING SYSTEMS**Mansurov T.***Professor, Doctor of Engineering Sciences, Professor, Department of Radio Engineering and Telecommunications, Azerbaijan Technical University, Baku***Kovalenko T.***Senior Lecturer, Master of Engineering Sciences, Department of Mathematics and Physics, Belarusian State Academy of Telecommunications***Mansurov E.***doctoral student, Department of Radio Engineering and Telecommunications, Azerbaijan Technical University, Baku***Abdulova N.***Associate Professor, Candidate of Engineering Sciences, Associate Professor, Department of Power Engineering, Sumgayit State University, Sumgayit***Jafarova B.***Senior Lecturer, Department of Computer Science and Algebra, Ganja State University, Ganja*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17878303>**Abstract**

This article analyzes the design principles of existing remote control systems for optical radiation direction in distributed monitoring systems. The disadvantages identified include the control time, which is an order of magnitude longer than the duration of transmitted pulses, and the fact that operation can only be controlled from the system's location. To address these concerns, a remote control system for optical radiation direction in distributed monitoring systems has been developed. This system enables remotely changing the direction of optical radiation and expands its functionality. This control system facilitates smooth changes in the direction of optical radiation within the range of 0° ... 360° . When inserted into telecommunication fiber, losses are 5...8 dB, which is 40...50% lower than in existing systems due to the reduced interaction area of the emitting surface of optical radiation.

Keywords: *telecommunication fiber, distributed monitoring system, optical radiation, spatial control, telecommunication network, all-optical network, optical component.*

Introduction

Optical technologies form the basis for the construction of modern telecommunications networks, and the main advantages of such networks are their high throughput and data security. Optical switches are most often used to construct devices for controlling the direction of optical radiation in distributed monitoring systems. The fastest of these are electro-optical switches, which operate on the principle of changing the refractive index of the working medium under the influence of an external electric field. All-optical networks are currently widely used, the main advantage of which is the presence of optical components that switch, filter, and regroup optical radiation. Consequently, all-optical networks are free from the disadvantages inherent in electronic components [1-5].

Therefore, the development of a system for remote control of the direction of optical radiation in distributed monitoring systems, the switching time of which is an order of magnitude shorter than the duration of sequentially transmitted pulses, is necessary. Existing systems are unable to ensure channel switching without losing information bits during commissioning and, furthermore, require an electronic control system.

The aim of this work is to develop a system for remote control of the direction of optical radiation in distributed monitoring systems.

Statement of the problem

One of the main challenges arising during optical transmission over fiber-optic communication lines is

the study of the fundamental principles of optical radiation injection into telecommunications fiber optics and the development of a system for remotely controlling the direction of optical radiation in distributed monitoring systems.

From a geometric optics perspective, it is necessary to determine the propagation trajectory of the guided optical radiation as a characteristic. This trajectory must be used to ensure high-precision switching of the telecommunications fiber, i.e., to deliver the maximum intensity of the output optical radiation to the telecommunications fiber at their mechanical connections. The problem of delivering the maximum intensity of optical radiation is further complicated by the lack of precise coordinates for the location of the transmitting/receiving system and the telecommunications fiber, meaning there is an angular divergence between them.

There are various options for constructing a system for controlling the direction of optical radiation in distributed monitoring systems [2-4], but their designs are complex and can only be controlled at the installation site. Furthermore, spatial control of the direction of optical radiation requires automatic vertical and horizontal alignment of the optical radiation relative to the end face of the telecommunications fiber to ensure that the optical radiation reaches the cladding boundary with its full intensity and is reflected into the fiber. Changing the direction of optical radiation is necessary because installation and laying of optical cables requires changing the laying direction from a distance by

a rotation angle greater than 90° . The degree of localization of the optical radiation field affects the size of the system, the speed, and the efficiency of optical radiation direction control. Therefore, expanding the range of practical applications requires the development of a system with new functional capabilities and characteristics, the development of a remote control system for optical radiation direction in distributed monitoring systems, and the research of new models and systems for switching the direction of optical radiation.

Development of a remote control system for the direction of optical radiation

To remotely switch telecommunication fibers and reduce energy loss during input/output of optical radiation in multimode telecommunication fiber and to develop a system for remotely controlling the direction of optical radiation in distributed monitoring systems, an analysis of the structure of existing systems for controlling the direction of optical radiation was conducted. Based on the conducted research, a remote control system for the direction of optical radiation was developed, allowing for remote smooth control of the direction of optical radiation in the range from 0° ... 360° [11,13]. This is achieved by introducing certain design modifications and changing the electronic control circuit and reducing the interaction area of the emitting surface of optical radiation with the multimode telecommunication optical fiber.

As can be seen from [6,11,12], control of the remote optical beam direction control system is only possible from the system's location. In some locations where optical cables are laid, access is difficult due to the cables passing through underground trenches and

manholes, as well as through subway tunnels. Therefore, it becomes necessary to control the optical beam direction remotely, for example, from mobile phones by entering the appropriate system code.

For this purpose, a switching system, mobile telephones connected to it via antennas (A), an answering machine (AM) and a series-connected receiving and transmitting device (RTD), a signal amplifier (SA), an analog-to-digital converter (ADC), an encoding device (ED), a digital code recognition and comparison device (DCRCD), the output of which is connected to the second control input of the trigger (T), are additionally introduced into the control circuit of the known system for remote control of the direction of optical radiation in distributed monitoring systems [12]; the first and second reference voltage units in the form of a digital code (BRC1 and BRC2), respectively, are connected to the second inputs of the digital code recognition and comparison device and the digital comparison device (DCD), and the second output of the receiving and transmitting device is connected to the input of the answering machine, the output of which is connected to the first input of the receiving and transmitting device, to the second input of which the second output of the logical key (LS) is connected. Mobile telephones, the telephone exchange and the receiving and transmitting device are connected to each other via antennas, respectively. The electronic blocks additionally introduced into the circuit of the proposed radiation direction switch are shown conditionally by dotted lines in the form of a block.

Fig. 1 shows the structural diagram of the developed system for remote control of the direction of optical radiation in distributed monitoring systems and its control diagram [12].

Fig. 1. Structural diagram of the remote control system for the direction of optical radiation in distributed monitoring systems with its control circuit

The operating principle of a remote control system for the direction of optical radiation in distributed monitoring systems

By dialing a digital code for the remote control system for optical radiation direction in distributed monitoring systems and sending a control signal via antennas, mobile phones are connected to the telephone exchange and, accordingly, to the receiving and transmitting device. An answering machine is automatically connected to the receiving and transmitting device, along with a code stored in it, corresponding to the position of the radiation direction of the transmitted signal, which is received by mobile phones. The signal is then amplified in a signal amplifier and converted into a digital code by an analog-to-digital converter. The digital signal is encoded by an encoding device and fed to the first input of the digital code recognition and comparison device. When the digital code voltage matches the voltage of the reference digital code block, a signal from the code recognition and comparison device is sent to the second control input of the trigger, switching it to another stable state. As a result, a signal from its output is sent to the signal input of the electronic key. The output voltage of the ultrasonic alternating voltage generator is then fed through the electronic key to the electrodes of the piezoelement (PE), causing the roller (B) to rotate. Rotation of the roller, which has a cylindrical surface with through radial holes (the cylindrical surface of the roller with through radial holes is not shown in Fig. 1), causes the holes to periodically open sequentially, resulting in a direct hit from a light-emitting diode (LED) and a photodiode

(PD). This light-emitting diode (LED) beam is simultaneously detected by a continuous pulse count, which, after being amplified by an operational amplifier, is fed to the input of the counter. When the pulse frequency in the form of a digital code is compared with the voltage of the reference digital code block, implemented by the digital comparator, a signal is generated at its output. This signal is fed through a logical switch to the first control input of the trigger, which is then transferred to another stable state. In this case, the voltage pulse from the trigger output, acting on the control input of the electronic switch, interrupts the AC generator circuit and the supply voltage to the piezoceramic element, which leads to immediate braking of the roller.

Methodology for determining the operational characteristics of a remote control system for the direction of optical radiation in distributed monitoring systems

The design of the proposed system for remotely controlling the direction of optical radiation in distributed monitoring systems involves rigidly mounting the beam reflector mirror on the shaft of a piezoelectric motor. The accuracy of optical radiation direction switching is determined by the alignment of the telecommunication fiber and the shaft openings. Switching accuracy depends on the flexural and deformation amplitude of the piezoelectric element, i.e., on the operational characteristics of this device and the accuracy of motor shaft stopping after braking. The motor's operational characteristics were determined through calculations and experiments.

The nominal torque on the shaft of a piezoelectric motor can be determined using the formula [7-11]:

$$M = F_T \cdot R, \quad (N \cdot m) \quad (1)$$

where R – is the shaft radius and $R = 14 \cdot 10^{-3} (m)$; F is the maximum tangential force acting from the T piezoelement of the shaft.

The maximum tangential force exerted by the piezoelectric element on the shaft is determined by the relationship:

$$F_T \approx U_{exc} \cdot l_2 \cdot d_{31} \cdot E_Y \cos \alpha. \quad (N) \quad (2)$$

Taking relationship (2) into account, equation (1) can be written as follows:

- for piezoelectric ceramics

$$M_1 \approx U_{exc} \cdot l_2 \cdot d_{31} \cdot E_Y \cos \alpha \cdot R, \quad (N \cdot m) \quad (3)$$

- for springs

$$M_2 = F_{sp} \cdot R, \quad (N \cdot m) \quad (4)$$

$$M_\Sigma = M_1 + M_2,$$

where $\sim U_{exc} = 200V$ – is the supply voltage of the alternating current generator, $l_2 = 1 \cdot 10^{-2} m$ – the thickness of the piezoelement; $d_{31} = 160 \cdot 10^{-12} (m/V)$ – the piezoelectric module; F_{sp} – the clamping force of the springs (N); M_Σ – the moment created by the tangential force and the force of the springs acting on the piezoelectric element (Nm), $E_Y = 0,7 \cdot 10^{11} (N/m^2)$ – Young's modulus, $\alpha = 45^\circ$ – the angle of inclination of the piezoelectric element to the shaft of the piezoelectric motor.

The shift amplitude Δ of the working end of the piezoelectric element in the shape of a prism taking into account the allowable excitation level $\sim U_{exc}$ is found by the following formula:

$$\Delta = \frac{2T_{cyc} \cdot l_1}{\pi \cdot E_Y}, \quad (m) \quad (5)$$

where $l_1 = 41 \cdot 10^{-2}$ – is the length of the piezoelectric element, (m).

Since

$$T_{cyc} \approx U_{leg} \cdot d_{31} \cdot Q_M \cdot E_Y, \quad (N) \quad (6)$$

where $\sim U_{leg} = 12500V/m$ – is the allowable electric field intensity.

Taking into account formula (5), equation (4) will take the form

$$\Delta = \frac{2 \sim U_{leg} \cdot d_{31} \cdot Q_M E_Y \cdot l_1}{\pi}. \quad (m) \quad (7)$$

The speed of movement of the piezo motor shaft in step mode

$$V_{mp} = \Delta \cdot f_p \cdot \cos \alpha \cdot K, \quad (m/s) \quad (8)$$

where $f_{rez} = 42 \cdot 10^3, Hz$ – is the resonance frequency of the supply voltage; $K = 0,14 \div 0,26$ – correction factor for the speed of movement of the shaft of a piezoelectric motor (determined experimentally taking into account the slippage of the working end of the piezoelectric element relative to the surface of the shaft of the piezoelectric motor).

Figure 2 shows the characteristic of the movement rate of the piezoelectric engine shaft depending on the moment $V_{mp} = f(M)$ created by the tangential force and the spring force acting on the piezoelement.

Fig. 2. Structural diagram of a remote control system for the direction of optical radiation in distributed monitoring systems
In accordance with formula (2), we find

$$F_T = 200 \cdot 6 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot 160 \cdot 10^{-12} \cdot 0,7 \cdot 10^{11} \cdot 0,73 = 9,81 (N),$$

$$M_1 = 9,81 \cdot 14 \cdot 10^{-3} = 0,13 (N \cdot m), \quad M_2 = 104 \cdot 14 \cdot 10^{-3} = 1,45 (N \cdot m),$$

$$M_\Sigma = 0,13 + 1,45 = 1,58 (N \cdot m).$$

In accordance with formula (5), we find

$$\Delta = \frac{2 \cdot 12500 \cdot 160 \cdot 10^{-12} \cdot 70 \cdot 41 \cdot 10^{-2}}{3,14} = 3,8 \cdot 10^{-6} \quad \mathcal{M} = 3,8 \text{ mkm}.$$

In accordance with formula (8), we find

$$V_{mp} = 3,8 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot 42 \cdot 10^3 \cdot 0,73 \cdot 0,2 = 98 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ m/s}.$$

The time required to start and establish mechanical vibrations of the piezoelectric element to 98%:

$$t_{st} = 1,47 \cdot \frac{Q_M}{f_{rez}} = \frac{40}{42000} = 0,0014 = 1,4 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ s},$$

where $Q_M = 200 \text{ unit}$ – is the mechanical quality factor piezoelement in the free (unsecured) state, and is the mechanical quality factor in the secured state due to mechanical losses $Q_M = 40 \text{ unit}$.

Conclusion

Thus, based on an analysis of the design principles of a remote optical beam direction control system in distributed monitoring systems, a system with expanded functionality has been developed. This system facilitates smooth changes in the optical beam direction of a transmitted signal over a range of $0^0\text{-}360^0$ and reduces switching times by an order of magnitude below the transmitted bit duration. Furthermore, when using this remote optical beam direction control system in distributed monitoring systems, the switching losses for telecommunication fiber and beam injection into the fiber of the optical cable are $5 \dots 8 \text{ dB}$, which is $40 \dots 50\%$ lower than in existing systems due to the reduced interaction area between the emitting surface of the optical beam and the telecommunication fiber.

The developed design of the remote optical beam direction control system in distributed monitoring systems offers significant advantages over existing electromechanical and magnetoelectric deflection systems. These include low power consumption, high mechanical strength, reliability, and manufacturability, as well as compact dimensions and cost. From a practical perspective, the proposed system for remote control of optical radiation direction in distributed monitoring systems can find application in optical information transmission systems.

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